

Investigating marketing of children's food stuff and methods of advertising in Iran

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ABSTRACT

Marketing of food stuff to increase sale is possible with different methods. Capillary marketing is one of the most influential techniques in the issue of more sales in organizations especially in terms of selling food stuff. Food stuff should be sold in a short time due to the short durability. People who make better use of capillary marketing to supply their products and services can sell better and faster. Dependency of Iran's economy on oil incomes and affectability of such incomes from political, economic and international issues cause vulnerability and fragility of the economy. One of the ways of coping with this situation is developing new products that improves inland economic condition and causes an increase in non-oil exports. Meanwhile, in addition to the role of food stuff in inland economic development, it can have a determining role in non-oil export. Most of the families don't have financial ability to respond steamy needs of their children. Such children are just happy with watching colorful food and being influenced by messages they don't tend to traditional food. In fact, advertisements tell children what to wear play and eat. In this study we are going to discuss marketing of children's food stuff and its advertising methods in Iran.

Keywords: food stuff marketing, advertising methods

Introduction

Food industry has the lowest dependency on foreign raw materials compared to the other industries and allocated 11% of industrial employment of the country for itself. (ministry of Jihad, 2015) the most important factors being investigated in the process of marketing by the managers of marketing include: product, way of distribution, determining the price, advancing sale, political power, public affairs and packaging. (Applied marketing, 2007) food advertisement on TV the goal of which consists of children and teenagers is one of the effective environmental factors in consuming food in this age range. (Lee B, Kim H, Lee S et al.) In this competitive world, the concept and function of marketing need to be reviewed and traditional techniques need to be reconsidered. However, reconsidering the concepts doesn't mean to put them away because marketers need to know traditional methods of marketing before accepting new and different ways of providing or implementing a new marketing plan (Mac Cool, 2004, 537). Schiffman and Kanuk (1997) state the fact that most of the consumers' behavior is based on economy and more precisely on the concept that when people buy something they logically seek benefits from their shopping. The model of Engel-Kollam – Blackwell (1995) emphasizes the importance of getting information about goods and services in the behavior of sale and consumption. This model manifests the relationship between the four components as following:

A. decision for shopping that is based on four levels:
 a. need b. looking for options c. evaluating options and d. behavior after shopping, B. attaining information, a consumer uses different resources to

get information and this influences his/her decision for shopping, C. processing data consists of providing, paying attention, understanding, accepting and protecting a customer while providing data, D. variables affecting the decision for shopping are related to the personal effects, reasons, values, life style, personality, environment, culture, reference groups and family.

Bettman (1979) emphasizes in his model that consumers rarely investigate complicated options related to the decision for shopping and they usually have a very simple strategy. This model has seven levels:

1. Ability to process information
2. Motivation
3. Attention and understanding
4. Searching information and evaluating them
5. Storing data
6. Process of making decision
7. Process of consumption and training.

Sheth- Newman – Gross's model (1991) states 5 values regarding the options of decision making that can influence consumers' behavior:

- a. functional value - arising from the features of products such as durability, price and etc.
- b. social value – consumers have some positive and negative models for buying an item which are related to some statistical variables such as age, sex, religion as well as social-economic variables such as level of income, employment and etc. and cultural variables such as race, religion and politics.
- c. emotional value- a time option that deals with emotions will enjoy emotional value,
- d. cognitive value- a decision-making option enjoys a cognitive value with some cases including curiosity, freshness, knowledge seeking and the need for attaining more information about an item,
- e. conditional value- a decision-making option will enjoy conditional value as a result of previous social and physical experiences.

Solomon's model (1996) discusses the following dimensions of consumers' behavior:

- a. buyer and consumer can be different people;
- b. people can influence the process of shopping;
- c.

organizations also can intervene the process of shopping; d. considerable part of marketing activities focuses on creating harmony between providing goods, addressee's needs and requirements; e. communication campaigns that create motivation for survival.

Middleton (1994) presented a model so-called stimulus- response. This model is based on four interactive components and the most essential ones include characteristics of a buyer and the process of decision-making. This model emphasizes important effects organizations can have on process of shopping by using the tool of combining communications.

In terms of making decision for shopping, Gilbert (1991) presented a model comprising two factors influencing the behavior of consumers. First factor includes psychological variables that are called perception and learning. Second one includes social-mental variables i.e. reference groups and family.

Schultz and Kitchen (2000) talk about the fact that one of the ways of promoting strategy is thinking about the content of message related to a consumer: when is the proper time for the message? At what times do the addressees react better to the message? By understanding seasonal tendencies, shopping cycles or ways of using goods and services we can send connection messages to organizations for enhancing efficiency. Considering customers' priorities and through making connection between such priorities and item/ brand, we can determine the time when a customer can respond the message better (Schultz and Kitchen 2000). Comprehensive marketing connections is a process through which the plans of connecting with current and potential customers, employees, organizations and the other addressees both inside and outside the organization can be developed, implemented and evaluated. The goal of comprehensive marketing connections is to create financial effects in a short while and making connections with customers in a long run (Belch, 2009).

The most important objectives of the study:

- * analyzing the relationship between comprehensive marketing connections and the behavior of food stuff consumer
- * determining factors that may influence the behavior of customers of food stuff through comprehensive marketing connections.
- * identifying tools used for collecting, processing and analyzing findings of the study

Definition of advertisement

Different definitions have been presented for advertisement; some people defined it as doing an organized activity for developing an idea or attracting people's attention to somebody or something and some others stated its meaning as saying, declaring, conveying and notifying in the dictionaries. In a French dictionary the definition of advertisement is mentioned as following:

A set of symbols and messages for an addressee in return for an specified price, organization, industrial item, brand or any other device being introduced to an addressee or encouraging him/her to an item or a service. In addition, in Larousse dictionary it is defined as: ways for introducing a commercial and industrial organization and its achievements. In another definition regarding commercial advertisement it is defined as: any kind of non-personal connections regarding an organization, a product, services or idea for which the sponsor pays (Holmes, 2009).

Different kinds of advertisement

Researchers of advertisement in the media divide it into ten groups based on the item being used: newspaper and journals, photos and film, cinema, post mail, radio, TV, poster, book and brochures, electronic boards in the streets, public areas and on the Internet. (Hirmet et al. 2013) on the other hand, divided advertisement into two general groups of commercial and non-commercial (advertising for idea,

ideology as well as social or political outlook). Additionally, there are other divisions such as service promotion (an advertisement promoting a service), advertisement along with music, dram advertisement (in the form of showing a special item) and state advertisement (in this kind of advertisement government will be responsible for supporting industry and production). Guarantying high and continuous sale, showing the importance of item compared to the similar ones, facilitation for distributors of sale, not forgetting the item by customers and being recorded in the minds are some cases being considered by researchers of this field for the goals of advertisement (Kumar& Raju, 2013).

Characteristics of advertisement

- a. like the process of social communication, advertisement includes receiver, transmitter, message and feedback;
- b. advertisement is published in return for the specified or agreed price;
- c. advertisers can advertise through different kinds of tools and social communication channels;
- d. advertisement is usually published for a special target group and advertisers have already known the political and social specifications of target group;
- e. goal of advertising is, in fact, persuading an addressee to buy. (Lee et al. 2014)

Indexes of successful advertisement

1. Advertisement should be continuous
2. If advertisement is published in audio and visual media, its time shouldn't be less than 30 seconds;
3. It should be stated or written in a language which is understandable for common people;
4. Before publishing, the target group should be specified and advertisers should consider their characteristics completely;

5. Before publishing an advertisement, conditions of the market, the likelihood of being welcomed and the state of sale must be evaluated.

Advantages of advertisement

1. Commercial advertisement gives the interlocutors proper information regarding the features of the item so that they get to know the prices and have the power to choose.

2. Commercial advertisements in the media will increase demand, thus more sales of especial goods or services and this can systematically lead to the improvement of working market and the reduction of unemployment.

3. Advertisement is an indirect way of investment and an opportunity for the media to gain money; it decreases prices because it encourages mass production. (Ansarian, 1998, 21)

Disadvantages of advertisement

Generally, although firms invest on advertisement assuming that it will increase sale, there has been some criticisms. For the first time advertisement was criticized in an American university, then a private community was established under the name of anti-advertisement community. This community criticized commercial advertisements, some of which are as follows:

1. The message being published in advertisements is more likely to be untrue.
2. Advertisement has negative effect on the society because it lacks truth;
3. Due to being continuously repeated in the media, advertisement will have negative effect on the addressees' spirit and taste.
4. Advertisement will increase class gap;
5. Consumerism, fashion and forgiving objects will be developed.

6. Companies with more financial power will get more powerful in the process of advertisement.

7. Advertisement will cause exclusive growth of big media. Big media monopolies harm smaller one by decreasing prices on the one hand and increasing coverage and giving space to advertisers on the other.

8. Advertisement is viewed as an action influencing people's mind entering their privacy and making them buy items they don't need or the ones that harm them.

9. In the process of the influence of advertisements, children are deceived easier than adults due social and cognitive growth.

10. Advertisement influences value systems and makes them inconspicuous.

11. Since advertisement is the media's source of income, people put them under pressure and change the content of the media directly and indirectly to their own benefit and if the media resists against this interference it will be deprived of financial support. (Fehrstorm, 2009)

General principles of commercial advertisement

In 1937, some principles were approved under the name of the basic principles of international regulations of advertising ethics in a congress in Berlin, Germany, the content of which is as follows:

Advertisement is a kind of media service for community whose success depends on the addressee's level of trust, therefore, no issue should ruin this trust. Considering the fact that one of the main reasons of success in advertisement is the effect of advertised item on the target addressee, no obstacle should foil or deactivate this effect. Companies and organizations must tell the truth in advertising their items and introduce their item without any exaggeration. Detailed specifications of the item such as weight, ingredients, price and after sale services must be declared in the advertisement. Pharmaceutical ads shouldn't be in a way that people consider using them

as the main treatment for their patience. (Yeboah & Atakora, 2013)

Predicting shopping behaviors of consumers based on Maslow's model

Limitation is the need itself and human has complicated needs. Abraham Maslow was a psychologist who made a research about successful people. He identified the hierarchy of human needs and divided them into five groups. In Maslow's view, as soon as the needs of level one are met, he will enter the second, third and the subsequent levels. In the following we are going to elaborate these levels and their relationship with the required items of consumers.

Level one: physiological needs

Such needs are the main components of humans' life such as food, water, shelter, air and sleeping. Those who are in this level probably don't have much money and providing food, shelter and basic equipment of life must be their top priority, thus, they will buy less expensive products even if they are low quality, because they can't afford better quality items. Such people tend to do anything that saves their money. (Pinegar, 2006)

Level two: safety needs

Such as the safety and peace you feel in your house, feeling of financial safety or having safe relationship with your friends and family members.

In this level consumers need to feel that they will be safe in the present and in the future. They will tend to buy items that give them more trust such as saving and pension funds, insurance, installing burglar alarm for home and car, taking classes of self-defense, weapon and etc.

Level three: love and belonging needs

Such as the methods a person chooses for being accepted in his/her intended group, the relationship he/she has with his/her friends and family and love of others to him/her. (Kris, 2004)

Being accepted is very important in this level. Everyone likes to keep fit with other people and no one likes to be labeled as alien, unusual or bizarre. In this level people try to follow the current norms in the community as much as possible, therefore, they will be accepted more by their fellows and peers. In addition, level three is the one in which people like to be with others. Most of the people don't like to be alone for ever that's why they are interested in things to make them more attractive to others especially to the opposite sex. In this level people will buy especial items such as the products with valid brand, proportionate clothes helping them to fit more with others and to be accepted by them, perfumes, cosmetics, and luxurious items. (Desjardins et al. 2014)

Level four: esteem needs

This level includes the need for self-esteem, respecting and to be respected, having authority and the need for being valuable. When we reach this level we will be ready to take care of ourselves better. Individuality is very important for people who are in this level. Because they are satisfied with themselves, have high self-esteem and they don't tend to be like any other person. Such people dress in an organized way so that they can be admitted by others. They get happy with the admission of others, but they are irritated less with others' criticism. At this level consumers like to be respected and appreciated by others. In level four people will buy the following goods and services for the aforementioned reasons:

Activities, devices, equipment and healthy food stuff to be healthier. Books helping them to be their own boss, because they want to have power and control conditions. Making investments and having bank accounts. Cloth, car and generally any expensive thing that gives them power to be superior over others. (Assadollahi et al. 2011)

Level 5: self-actualization needs

At this level an individual feels that he/she attained whatever he/she could attain. If somebody reaches

this level, he/she will long for peace, knowledge and perfection. This is the last level and unfortunately most of the people never reach this level during their lives. However, people who reach this level feel satisfied with themselves and the kind of life they have had. They buy things that make them and others happy. (Zaltman, 1995)

The effect of advertisement and marketing on children's food behavior

With regard to different behaviors of consumers, the business of advertisement and its effect on children especially today's children who are exposed to advertisements more and are more vulnerable have been increased considerably in the last two decades. (Asadollahi et al. 2011) children as potential customers are the main target group of marketers because in addition to spending money on junk food, sweets and toys they influence their parents in the process of making decision for shopping. In addition, advertisement influences the portion and type of food stuff being consumed by children. In Iran most of the advertisements are for junk food and especially the one with low nutritional value containing high fat, simple sugars and salt. (Amini et al. 2007)

Methods of advertising children's food stuff

In today's world providing nutritional information about food through cell phone is an important necessity. Food stuff marketing through cell phone often focuses on discounts and prevailing that, but consumers think about something beyond reducing prices. They look for information. This is not that strange that the studies of Deloitte business consulting institute in March 2010 suggested that about 25 percent of such people use cell phone for getting information about the features of items. Such information is attained online by referring to the website of different brands. In April 2010, Latitude research institute investigated this issue more. According to this survey at different times people tend to have more information about hygiene and health, quality of an item, price and the location of sale. This study has recently been carried out among the

American community. On this basis, 51 percent of people believe that mentioning the name of manufacturing country on fresh meat is very important. 54 percent of them always or often don't pay attention to nutritional information on that. In the second level, people were asked to name the best way for receiving such information. To reply most of them mentioned using mobile and access to the Internet as the most suitable ways. Super markets must note that 51 percent of people consider the information provided by department stores as the best suggestion for success. Recently, most of the food stuff brands tend to provide some information about their products themselves and guide their customers by presenting some information about their genetically modified productions by mobile. Therefore, it cannot be accepted why a food stuff brand with new technologies hasn't won customers' trust yet and make them loyal. Indicating the name of manufacturing country and the calories of special food can help them in this path. Investigations of August 2010 anticipated that food sellers can increase the number of customers using their mobile technologies. Anyway, it is important not to forget that customers will go to other stores if they don't receive any information about items via mobile. (Spencer Jonson, 2003)

Traditional sale

Selling is one of the oldest professions and maybe it is one of basics forming the community and the means of meeting humans' needs. In its traditional form we picture shops of business men and then in today's world there are networks, virtual world and competitive markets, all of which are examples of sale. But paradigms and concepts are what have been changed about sale that are the effect of events, fundamental developments of industry and supply chain. In the traditional space of selling, most of the selling activities were taking orders and making long lines of customers due to low supply and non-competitiveness of selling space or low knowledge of customers regarding exact parameters of products and their alternative items led to the impose of low quality and exclusive items on customers. In addition, mental

image of selling in the traditional system was based on a talkative, flattering and somehow lying character; however, most of these concepts undergone radical changes during the last decades. Maybe, now we can say that past images of sale can no longer meet customers' and sellers' needs in today's complicated formula and calculations because regulations, dominant paradigms and the needs governing new markets (twenty-first century) are quite different from the past.

Techniques of sale in marketing

Sale is a kind of helping others to promote the quality of their job and life. In the recent years, it has changed dramatically. Competitions and the number of sellers have been increased. Those who want to attract more customers must be smarter and their clothing, talking and walking are also important. Competing in sale is similar to competing in sport matches i.e. if you don't keep training and practicing your rival will win. If you don't continuously get better, for sure you will get worse and you will be considered in the low 80 percent group. (Brian Tracy, 2005)

Identifying target group

Who are really your customers? Where are they from? How old are they? How much is their average income? What about the average of their education? The more your information about your customers or target group, the better you can choose your customers. Then, instead of grabbing your gun and starting to shoot you can take your bow and arrow and take aim. The fact is that none of the customers care about you, your company and your product. They just observe what you are doing for them to live more comfortably.

What considerable change can you make in the quality of their lives? For example, if a customer wants to get insured, he/she has no reason but to feel safe and feeling safe means promoting quality of life and improving life. So, you should advertise your products and services and tell your customers about the advantages of your product clearly. A customer

must understand that you identified the features of his/her required item and could supply a product that even if not the best it is one of the best in the market. You must keep asking yourself this question that why a customer buys one of your items and doesn't buy another one? If you keep a blind eye on this fact, you won't be a successful seller (David, 2002).

Reference, the most important key of sale

Reference is the most important key of sale. Has it ever happened to you that you bought an item and after shopping you got to know that they pulled the wool over your eyes? If it happened to you, always doubt the seller. This has happened for customers at least once, thus, they are always doubtful, whether in Iran or any other place in the world. You must ensure you customer to eliminate his/her fear and doubt. Therefore, your words and clothing get important. It is important to be man of your word as well as the features that, in fact, are the criteria of the customer's judgment of your personality and honesty. In this journey, I went to one of the restaurants in Tehran and I found it very crowded. I asked about that restaurant and they said "it is always like this here and people introduce here to their friends and acquaintances". This means right function. If you spend enough time and energy on your first customer, you can spend the next customer who is a reference customer one tenth of the time you spent for the previous one. (Tracy, retrieved from Tehran seminar)

Responding disagreements of a customer

Ability to respond disagreements of customers is an effective skill in the issue of sale. The more a customer asks you, the more you must get interested in answering him/her, because asking questions means the customer liked your product. You must not get angry while answering. If a customer asks a question and you don't answer you will be a loser. You must predict your customers' questions in advance and prepare some answers. (Batra, simple ways for the descent career of selling)

Communicative method

A customer won't buy anything from you unless he/she feels that you care about him/her. It is very important that your customer feels safe while talking to you. Your words must remove his/her fear and doubt. So, don't cut your relationship with your customers after shopping because this relationship will lead to the reference of next customers. For a successful seller, selling is the beginning of a relationship not ending that. So, focus on communication.

Techniques of sale in marketing

Invitation technique

The simplest technique for finalizing sale is inviting a customer to buy:

If you like this why don't you try it?

Most of the customers are on the edge of making decision for shopping. While they are making decision for buying something, they remember bad experiences they had in their previous shopping. Then, they say: "I don't need it...I don't know". But, a good seller never lets any sale go without inviting a customer.

Replacement technique

If a customer has more than one option and he/she is in doubt which one to choose, you should ask him/her which one he/she likes. We all like to have many options. But, if there is only one option, create some:

Is it expensive? We will give you a discount, how much do you have in cash? We will let you pay on installment plan.

Caring technique

Customers must feel that even if they are wrong in choosing, you care for them and don't leave them alone. This feeling is very pleasant for customers. How to use this technique in your sale is up to you. Customers are in doubt even in the last moments of buying something. So, if you ensure them saying there

is no reason for concern they will be relieved and take a long step toward buying that item.

Secondary technique

Another technique of sale in marketing is secondary technique. If your customer wants to buy a car, focus on a secondary issue on buying a car not on the main issue of buying itself. For example, say "how is the color? Do you like this color?" color is a secondary factor. The main issue is the car itself, but you will finalize sale by asking such questions.

Steep angel technique

In this technique of marketing you must go ahead based on disagreements. For example, a customer says: "this is very expensive", you answer: you can take this and pay on installment plan, can you pay the installments? He/she answers: "well I need it for tomorrow", you say: alright, how about making it ready by dusk?

That is as soon as he/she disagrees, you block the way in the same angel.

Permission technique

Humans like to be asked for permission. So, don't force customers. You should talk to him/her in a way that he/she has option. For example, say: do you let this be done? He/ she will decide to say yes or no. (Hyman and Sanchez, 2012)

Conclusion

Today, consumers have been exposed to different data resources and comprehensive marketing connections have become very important. Campaigns of comprehensive marketing connections that are highly considered rely on the power of connection tools for influencing addressee's behavior. Designing an effective message and choosing efficient connection tools are important levels in creating and maintaining consumers' priorities for goods and services. Comprehensive marketing connections include activities that create influential connections with customers and put value on the item or the brand of a

company. Goal of this connection is to make sure about appropriateness and the content of conveyed message through combining marketing tools such as advertisements, promoting sale, direct marketing, public relations, online connections and so on. The knowledge created for the customers by having access to the connections can specify their priorities for the way they receive information. An organization can be benefitted from comprehensive marketing connections effectively and economically by considering expectations of customers.

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